

UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS' SCIENCE ENGAGEMENT IN USING CHATBOT AS PREDICTOR TO THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN CHEMISTRY

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ABSTRACT

In this era, known as the “digital age,” technology is viewed as necessary components of daily life. It only makes sense for educational institutions like schools to successfully employ technology like chatbot integration in classroom, given their increasing popularity among the students. This paper investigated the impact of chatbot engagement and class participation on freshmen students' in their academic performance in chemistry at Norzagaray College. Using a quantitative research design, the study involved 88 first-year Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) students. Based on the results of the study, it was revealed that there is a high level of chatbot engagement (mean = 3.39) and participation (mean= 3.36) of students in Chemistry. However finding also revealed that although chatbot has high impact to engagement and participation of students there was no significant correlation found between students' science engagement using chatbot ($r = 0.117$; $p = 0.280$) and class participation ($r = 0.041$; $p = 0.705$) in their academic performance. This implies that although chatbot assist student in the learning process, but it is not necessary guarantee them to get a high grades.

Keywords: *chatbot, academic performance, science engagement, AI in education, chemistry education, personalized learning, virtual assistants*

INTRODUCTION

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in the field of education has a great impact to our learners just like our life anchored on Science. This AI-powered tools offer us numerous advantages this include personalized learning experiences, basic process skills and develop basic scientific knowledge or concepts. Employing this technological tool to education has a bright future to create a informal learning inside and outside of the classroom. Aside from that there is undeniable fact that more students are spending more time using different technological tool to support their academic endeavors.

A chatbot, also known as a bot, is a type of software program that simulates or imitate human conversation through text and voice interactions over the internet and mobile phone. This chatbot make students lives easier because they can access information through their electronic gadgets. This software has access to an endless amount of data and information since this chatbot can be used as educational assistant offer 24/7 availability. Their ability to understand is very impressive they can respond to human language makes a relevant answer to any various questions, from virtual assistants to online customer support systems. (Pérez et al., 2020).While chatbot development is undeniably very useful in every field it is also have many specialized technical skills like different platforms provided by different companies like Microsoft, Facebook, Google, and LINE have significantly simplified the process (Abdellatif et al., 2020). Effective usage of chatbot may have good effects on efficient work and help them to multitask.

The integration of chatbot technology, especially Chat GPT into educational settings is very useful especially to the learners who have a hard time in their academic performance; this tool can help students a lot due to the widespread adoption of smart phones among learners (Okonkwo & Ade-Ibijola, 2021). Since it is available to everyone, we can all have it on our device. These chatbots can be highly beneficial especially it can offer them a personalized learning, acting as free virtual tutors, and even assisting with their writing and even with their assignments (Hong, 2023). These chatbot can provide benefits such as quick access to information for students, diverse ways of learning, contextual learning control over own learning, support encouragement of learning, increase participation in the course, will to use in the course, and positive meaningful difference in academic achievement. However, like any other tool, there is a potential negative impact especially to the learners. Some experts said that excessive used on chatbots may lead to students' lack of development to their critical thinking and problem-solving skills and also tend to become very dependent to this chatbots. Teacher guidance in integrating this tools for maximizing the benefits while understanding their potential drawbacks and creating a learning environment that suited for building a critical thinking and independent learning (Ali et al., 2023).

In recent years, the growing gap between the increasing number of students to teacher worsened every year by increasing their gap ratio (Essel et al., 2022), it affect our educational system this factor need to he considered why students tend to used chatbot. In some case students' reluctance to ask questions due to shyness and fear of

negative feedback (Oktaria & Soemantri, 2021) in this case students tend to shift towards chatbots for immediate assistance to their queries. This AI tutors, powered by chatbot give them a personalized support and intelligent feedback in subjects like mathematics without fear to get some negative feedback to others, they used it in programming, and even in language learning. Platforms such as Duolingo leverage advanced AI systems to enhance the learning experience (Bicknell et al., 2023), this platform give them independence to learn by their own pace, having a confidence to do some various task, and engagement to some activities. By that students build and developed their critical thinking skills through inquiry and by exploring a diverse perspective.

Using this chatbots are becoming relevant in education, particularly in situations where instructors cannot provide immediate feedback to students. These AI-powered tools can simulate human-like conversations, allowing students to easily access learning resources and immediate receiving assistance particularly for those who reside in rural and remote areas. It also gives engagement in interactive learning experiences. This versatility of chatbots has definitely has a great way for improving students experience and learning.

Additionally, chatbots can also be valuable tools for students who need help in making homework. These AI-powered tools are capable to give assistant and detailed feedback on their assignments. It also can also used as a tool to identify the areas for improvement and suggesting further learning resources by asking them (Celik et al., 2022). For instance, chatbots can act as study companions, they will give you some explanations and even clarify on every various things that you need to know about lesson that we may not fully grasped in the classroom. This tools can assist students with their homework by just simply type the problem and it will provide step-by-step solutions in an instance and guiding students through complex problems (Crawford et al., 2023; Fauziet al., 2023; Lo, 2023; Shidiq, 2023).

However, the potential for chatbots to exacerbate pre-existing biases such as in language and perpetuate societal inequalities is a concern that can be mitigated through appropriate training and monitoring measures. Potential for giving misinformation, by asking them without clear questions. This chatbot also have the potential to disseminate misinformation if their training datasets are biased or inaccurate, or if their programming prioritizes engagement at the expense of accuracy. The potential violation of privacy may occur if chatbots are utilized to gather and scrutinize some sensitive personal data without your consent so always be mindful when we using it. In another study by Kohnke et al. (2023), it is mentioned that chatbots have a risk of causing ethical violations and in some instances it can give misleading answers to their users that lead to confusion of the users. Moderation used should be appropriate with the academic demands for the sake of the learning process.

By understanding how chatbots impact our learning and skill development in many field like science subjects it can give some strategies to improved out technology integration, leading us for more effective and engaging science education. This research is beneficial to educators and first-year college students by helping them to improve

accessibility to learning resources and support by enhancing the learning experience for occasion. This prompted the researchers to conduct this study to investigate the impact of chatbot engagement on first-year college students' academic performance in chemistry, with the objective of determining whether chatbots contribute positively to student learning outcomes during this critical stage. The findings of this study are expected to provide insights into whether the engagement of chatbots helps first-year college students improve their academic performance in chemistry.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

Science classrooms are embracing a new learning companion such as chatbots. These tools can give us interactive and meaningful learning experiences by simply asking questions, getting help with experiments. In this technological tool can give teachers an idea on how they can build a new ways to make their lessons more engaging and personalized by using this chatbots they can help students understand science in a fun and exciting way.

The technology evolved so fast this include as virtual and augmented reality, learning management systems, and artificial intelligence that will lead us to a new pedagogical approaches and give innovative teaching strategies and even in our assessment methods in classroom. These development help teacher and students to develop a modern style of learning with the integration of chatbot. Furthermore, modern learning was a learning style that would develop to set skills of the students with the use of benefits of technology advancement for exploration and preparation to the realities of the modern workplace. These technological innovations are influence our student in every aspect of their life by continuous technological changes and improvement learners also evolved their learning process (Sürmelioglu & Seferoglu, 2019).

Besides to the traditional ways of learning where basically teacher centered, there's a new approach called "flexible personalized learning" that uses AI-powered chatbots. This approach use an AI smart tutors that can give students needs by giving them individual guidance and feedback, helping them to understand some difficult topics (Boateng & Tindi, 2022). These chatbots aim to help the students to development new knowledge, just like teacher do (Han & Lee, 2023; Pérez et al., 2020).

According to Boateng and Tindi (2022), to make learning more engaging, students utilized this chatbots often, it can also be found in many messaging platforms like Telegram or We Chat, making it easy for students to interact with this platform. This platform is very accessible, that we all know that all individual nowadays are having mobile phone. These chatbots can be used to adapt any forms of teaching style to fit of what student's needs (Fariani et al., 2023; Kikalishvili, 2023). The two of the most popular AI-powered chatbots are Chat GPT and Google Bard. These two chatbots are designed on a huge amount of text and code, which allows them to generate text, create different types of content, and answer questions, although they might not always be perfectly accurate they are very useful. Since students can use chatbot like Chat GPT anytime anywhere, it makes learning more convenient for them. Researchers have found that

Chat GPT's conversational style can make learning more enjoyable and personalized, increasing student engagement and motivation (Kasneci et al., 2023).

In the study of Chamorro-Atalaya (2023) reviewed that acceptance and effectiveness of chatbots in some university in education adopted a technology in fostering a learning environments. The research highlighted that chatbots can enhance some various learning activities by applying some student interactions during to their learning process. It suggests that using some technological advancement like chatbots provide a positive impact on having a learning outcome.

Along with Almada (2023) it is suggested by developing a proactive chatbot with natural language processing and the k-means clustering algorithm to help students with failing grades. The research focuses on a long-standing problem of early identification and intervention for students experiencing academic difficulties by presenting a model that recognizes and assists students based on their modified academic characteristics. Although the opinions and perceptions of each teacher are frequently taken into consideration when deciding whether to employ technology in the classroom.

Also, a study at Georgia State University found that a chatbot called "Pols Pounce" significantly improved the final grades of students in an American government course (Meyer et al., 2022). This chatbot can helps students to create a personalized message asked this tool to remind them to finish their task and even answers their questions. They concluded that 8% of students who used chatbot are likely to get or higher in the course. Also in their research found that using chatbot can have impact to having a greater improvement and increasing their grade by 11 percentage points. These findings suggest that chatbots can be an important tool to improve the student learning outcomes, but take note it is important to note that chatbots are not a replacement for human instructors.

In contrast, various studies suggest that while chatbot is not necessarily boosting academic performance although chatbot can positively influence student motivation and engagement. Yin et al. (2021) observed that undergraduate students using a chatbot showed increased motivation, even without significant differences in their academic performance. This aligns with Arruda et al. (2019), who found that a chatbot designed for computer science students was a helpful and desirable for future use. Similarly, Kamita et al. (2019) found chatbots used alongside web courses for mental health support to be effective by providing guiding self-learning, boosting student motivation, and reducing stress. Their findings suggest that although chatbots can positively affect the motivation and engagement in the learning process it might not always lead to high grades.

In the K-12 science curriculum, teaching Science across grade levels involves a variation of complex and abstract concepts and ideas that show how students may find science as a challenging subject to grasp on their own. In that case that the student face hindrance to learn the teachers may break down some concepts into easy to understand and with the use of chatbot to help student especially those undergraduate with their

task, activities and academic performance. Through this kind of technique, some of the students are able to do their class works by using different technological support to access with different topics especially with Science related topics. By doing that their knowledge bridges the gap between theory and practice, allowing student to take the challenges more easily to face off.

Integrating technology such as chatbot can give better outcome in teaching science by utilizing it as a supplement to enhance the learning experience of the students. This technology tool have potential to significantly change the education of Filipino students by visualizations, and virtual experiments that make learning materials more tangible and 6 engaging for students. It also open door to explore more to achieve learning experiences more fruitful. By leveraging technology in science education, teachers can empower students to explore and understand challenging scientific ideas in a more interactive and in fun way.

Conceptual Framework

The investigation was anchored on the Information Processing Theory which views the mind as a system that receives, processes, stores, and retrieves information, provides a valuable framework for understanding how a chatbot can impact student learning in science.

This theory suggests that a chatbot can act as a tool to support students in processing and accessing information more efficiently. By providing instant answers, explanations, and feedback, a chatbot can help students navigate the stages of information processing, from input and processing to storage and retrieval. This, in turn, can lead to improved understanding, retention, and application of scientific concepts, ultimately enhancing academic performance in science.

Paradigm of the Study

In Figure 1, engagement and class participation with the chatbot is the independent variable, while academic performance is the dependent variable. The arrow indicates that chatbot engagement and participation may influence learners' academic performance in chemistry. The level of engagement and participation with the chatbot is expected to impact the academic performance of learners.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the use of chatbots as a predictor of academic performance among undergraduate students in chemistry.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How may the students' science engagement in using chatbot be described?
2. How may the students' class participation in Chemistry be described?
3. How may the academic performance of student in Chemistry be described?
4. Do students' science engagements in using chatbot and class participation significantly predict their academic performance in Chemistry?
5. What program can be developed based on the result of the study?

Hypothesis

The study was guided and tested by the hypothesis below: Engagement and Class participation with the Chatbot Academic Performance in Chemistry 7 Students' science engagement in using chatbot and class participation do not predict their academic performance in Chemistry.

Significance of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the use of chatbots as a predictor of academic performance among undergraduate students in chemistry. The research findings may help students to understand on how using chatbots can potentially improve their academic performance. This leads to give them a better study strategies and a better understanding of their progress. Teachers can also benefit from this research by learning how to use chatbots in their classes to improve student learning. By connecting technology with learning objectives so that chatbot use will have an educational purpose and applications, because although students use their devices on their own, they would benefit more if their instructors found deliberate uses for these powerful tool to meet the specific needs of their students. Moreover, this study will also serve as a guide to future researchers by offering an idea for how to evaluate the impact of chatbot engagement on academic performance and providing a basis for further exploration in the field of technology-enhanced in chemistry education.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research utilized a quantitative research design with a descriptive evaluation and descriptive correlation to investigate the relationship of chatbot as predictor to engagement and class participation on academic performance in chemistry among first-year BSED students. The study employed a descriptive approach by analyzing existing

data on student performance in chemistry, specifically focusing on the correlation between chatbot engagement and participation to their academic outcomes.

Respondents and Sampling

The study involved all 88 first-year BSED students from Norzagaray College as respondents. The selection of participants utilized the total population, ensuring representation from both BSED 1A (population of 40) and BSED 1B (population of 48). This approach will provide a comprehensive understanding of the use of chatbots among the entire first-year BSED student population at Norzagaray College.

Instrumentation

The researchers investigate undergraduate students' engagement using chatbots as a predictor of their academic performance in chemistry.

Science Engagement and Class Participation Using Chatbot

To assess engagement and class participation using a chatbot, the researchers utilized a modified Likert scale instrument adapted from Riggs (2024) containing 20 items that is divided into two parts: 10 items for student engagement and 10 items for class participation. Each item will be answered by (1) Strongly Disagree; (2) Disagree; (3) Agree; (4) Strongly Agree. The reliability of the scale was measured through Cronbach's alpha, resulting in a reliability range from 0.78 to 0.93; this range is considered acceptable.

Academic Performance

To assess the academic performance, the researchers utilized existing and reliable data from the class records maintained by the chemistry teacher. This approach ensured the use of comprehensive data that reflected students' overall performance in the chemistry course. The class record data provided a comprehensive measure of academic performance, encompassing various assessments and assignments throughout the semester.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before initiating the research on investigating the impact of chatbot engagement on academic performance in chemistry among first-year BSED students at Norzagaray College, the researchers obtained permission from the President of the school and to the Dean of the College of Education. Adhering to Regional Memo No. 228, s. 2020, ethical guidelines were followed to ensure confidentiality, informed consent, and participant briefing on the study's objectives, duration, and potential risks and benefits. Data handling procedures included strict confidentiality measures and secure storage. The study involved 88 first-year BSED students.

Upon receiving approval from the School's Academic Office, the data-gathering procedure for the participating first-year undergraduate BSED students began. The researchers administered the questionnaires using Google Form to the respondents through Facebook Messenger Group Chats, and consent and assent letter were used, with clear instructions provided before administering the actual questionnaire. The gathered responses were checked to ensure they satisfied the required number of samples.

The data gathered from research competencies and perceived difficulties in thesis writing were tabulated in Jamovi, statistical spreadsheet software. Data analysis involved the use of Pearson's r correlation coefficient to analyze the quantitative data collected. The mean were utilized to describe the science engagement, students' class participation and academic performance in Chemistry in using chatbot. Pearson's r correlation was used to determine if there are significant relationship between students' science engagement in using chatbot and class participation to predict their academic performance in Chemistry.

RESULTS

Table1. Demographic Profile in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	percentage
Male	18	20.5%
Female	70	79.5%
Total	88	100%

Table 2. Demographic Profile in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	percentage
18-21	75	85.2%
22-24	13	14.8%
Total	88	100%

Table 3. Science Engagement in Using Chatbot.

No.	Item Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I want to ask my science teacher or classmates personally or through social media if I have a trouble understanding a lesson	3.52	Strongly Agree
2	My science lessons and performance tasks are realistic and contextualized in the Chatbot.	3.59	Strongly Agree
3	I am inspired to learn new things in science class through Chatbot.	3.34	Strongly Agree

4	My science lessons and task in Chatbot stimulate my curiosity.	3.30	Strongly Agree
5	I feel encouraged and interested to work on something in science class with the integration of Chatbot.	3.34	Strongly Agree
6	My science lessons and tasks in the Chatbot are interesting and meaningful.	3.27	Strongly Agree
7	I appreciate the nature of scientific method or process.	3.41	Strongly Agree
8	I am inspired and prepared to come to science class every day with the integration of Chatbot	3.31	Strongly Agree
9	I always pay attention to my teacher and classmates who communicate during science class.	3.48	Strongly Agree
10	I follow the instructions closely in doing my science work with the integration of Chatbot.	3.30	Strongly Agree
Overall		3.39	Strongly Agree

*Scale: 1.00 – 1.75=Strongly Disagree; 1.76 – 2.50 =Disagree; 2.51 – 3.25 =Agree; 3.26 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

Table 4. Students Class Participation in Science

No.	Item Statement	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1	I raise my hand to participate in science class discussions.	3.36	Strongly Agree
2	I do and finish my science tasks on time.	3.45	Strongly Agree
3	I participate and interact during small-group discussions in Science.	3.39	Strongly Agree
4	I prepare thoroughly before the test to be conducted in Chatbot.	3.17	Agree
5	I am having fun during collaborative learning activities in science with the integration of Chatbot	3.39	Strongly Agree
6	My science lessons and performance tasks are important and relevant to my life.	3.39	Strongly Agree
7	I want to investigate and understand the societal and environmental impacts and implications from Science and technology.	3.27	Strongly Agree
8	I consult and share my views and knowledge to my classmates and Science teacher	3.30	Strongly Agree

9	I read and review my modules, class notes, handouts, and textbook between classes to make sure that I learn from these Science learning materials.	3.41	Strongly Agree
10	I give maximum effort to my science class	3.51	Strongly Agree
Overall		3.36	Strongly Agree

*Scale: 1.00 – 1.75=Strongly Disagree; 1.76 – 2.50 =Disagree; 2.51 – 3.25 =Agree; 3.26 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

Table 5. Total mean of Academic Performance

	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Academic Performance	88.3	Good

*Scale:100-96.5=Excellent; 96.4-93.4=Superior; 93.4-90.5=VeryGood; 90.4-87.5=Good 87.4-84.5=VerySatisfactory; 84.4-81.5=HighAverage; 81.4-78.5=Average; 78.4-75.5=Fair 75.4-74.5= Pass

Table 6. Pearson's r Correlation Matrix

Academic Performance	Pearson's r	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Science engagement in using Chabot.	0.117	0.280	Not Significant	Do not Reject the null hypothesis
Academic Class Participation	0.041	0.7.5	Not Significant	Do not Reject the null hypothesis

Note. *p< .05, **p<.01, ***p<.001

DISCUSSION

Table 1. Shows that the demographic profile in terms of sex indicates a sample size of 88 individuals, with 18 males representing 20.5% and 70 females accounting for 79.5% of the total. The data reveals a higher proportion of females in the sample population, highlighting a gender imbalance with females being the majority.

Table 2. Shows that the demographic profile in terms of age comprises a total sample size of 88 individuals, with 75 individuals (85.2%) falling in the 18-21 age group and 13 individuals (14.8%) in the 22-24 age group. The data indicates a significant majority of individuals in the 18-21 age range, suggesting that the sample is primarily composed of young adults.

Table 3. Shows a high level of undergraduate students' engagement in using a Chatbot reveals a strong impact to their learning process. The overall mean engagement score is 3.39, indicating a high level of agreement among students, indicating that using chatbot boosts their eagerness to learn more. This suggests that the Chatbot is generally contributed to student engagement positively to the learning experience. This finding supports the study of Chamorro-Atalaya (2023) and Kasneci et al. (2023), who found that chatbots can enhance students learning activities by fostering student interactions, increasing engagement, and providing personalized feedback to their work, and suggesting that technological advancements like chatbots can positively impact their learning engagement.

Table 4. Shows that the undergraduate students' participation in science reveals a strong commitment to learning. The overall mean participation score of 3.36 indicates a high level of agreement among students regarding their participation, indicating a positive attitude towards their involvement in science-related activities. This finding aligns with research suggesting that interactive learning tools can enhance student engagement and motivation to participate. Studies like Kamita et al. (2019) and Topal et al. (2021) suggest that chatbots can be used in self guided learning, enhance motivation, and even improve mental health of the students to be more active in the classroom. These findings suggest that incorporating chatbots into science education could contribute to a more engaging and supportive learning environment, potentially leading to increased student participation in science-related activities.

Table 5. Shows that the mean of academic performance of 88.3 suggests that students have demonstrated a good level of understanding and mastery of the Science related activities, but may need some additional support or practice to reach their full potential. The fact that most students grade between 87.4 and 90.5 indicates that there may be a "ceiling" effect, where students have reached a certain level of proficiency but are not yet achieving at an exceptional level. This observation aligns with research suggesting that while chatbots may not always lead to significant improvements in academic achievement, they can positively impact student motivation. Yin et al. (2021) found no significant difference in learning achievements between students who used a chatbot and those who did not. However, the study reported higher levels of motivation among students who interacted with the chatbot. This suggests that while chatbots might not directly improve test scores, they can be very helpful in keeping engagement and encouraging students to continue learning.

Table 6. Shows that the Pearson's r correlation calculated for science chatbot engagement and students participation has no significant correlation found between students' science engagement using chatbot ($r = 0.117$; $p = 0.280$) which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. In class participation ($r = 0.041$; $p = 0.705$) which also greater

than the alpha value of 0.05 so both null hypotheses are not rejected. Therefore, it was found that although chatbot may be used to support the learning process of the students' engagement and participation in Science, they are not guaranteed that using chatbot will lead them to high grades. The result of the findings contrasts to Meyer et al. (2022), which concludes that using chatbot can improve academic performance. They found that 8% of the students were more likely to get a B or higher in the course, with their grades increasing by 11 percentage points.

These findings suggest that chatbots can be an important tool to improve student learning outcomes. In the study of Boonmoh et al. (2021) mentioned that the knowledge of students when it comes to technology and using different technological tools also has an impact on the effectiveness of technology integration in school. So therefore, it is not about how often you use the chatbot, but rather about how you utilize and apply it to enhance your own understanding. Chatbot can be used to come up with a program to improve chemistry students' academic performance.

The program being proposed by the researchers will help to design and utilize a chatbot-assisted learning system for college-level students in chemistry which will assist them in improving their academic achievement and other outcomes related to their studies. This program aims to improve the BSED students' learning outcomes in Chemistry by giving them immediate assistance and easy access to the information, we hope to increase their motivation, engagement, participation together with their academic performance.

Propose program	Timeline	Resources
* Integrate Chatbot into the curriculum for example create a chatbot platform exclusive for chemistry-related studies, encourage use of chatbot as a supplement for traditional teaching.	*1-2 months for chatbot integration and platform.	*Development team for chatbot platform.
*Training and support for Chemistry teachers on how to effectively integrate Chatbot in their teaching practice, and provide technical support to the students who need assistance.	*1-2 months Training and support for chemistry instructors.	*Instructors for training and support staff.
*Regular evaluation of students' learning outcomes to their academic performance such as quizzes and exams.	*1 whole semester evaluation and polishing of the program.	*Evaluation tools and other materials.

Conclusions

This study revealed that although chatbots can encourage students to be more engaged and actively participate in the classroom. Finding also revealed that chatbot can't necessary guarantee them to improved their academic performance. Furthermore, in terms of support chatbot can help students to become more independent learners, more confident to their abilities and better solver to their problem. Moreover, chatbot can enhance students learning experience by learning more accessible regardless on time or location. However, despite of positive engagement and participation level of participants in this research, there is still a need of improvement to reach higher level of proficiency. Therefore, this indicates that while chatbots can help students to enhance their motivation and engagement, they do not necessarily rely on chatbots to improve their academic performance.

Recommendations

The researchers formulate some recommendations based on the findings of the study, to improve the academic performance of the students as well as their engagement experience.

1. **Enhance Chatbot Functionality.** To address the needs of students and learning gaps, chatbot may incorporate features that will offer more personalized feedback and adaptive learning paths. Additionally, to maintain the interest of students and to deepen their understanding, chatbot might also consider adding more interactive and engaging elements like quizzes, simulations, and gamification.
2. **Combine Chatbot with Other Teaching Methods.** Complement chatbot engagement with traditional teaching methods and friendly learning activities that will create a holistic learning exposure.
3. **Provide More Support and Resources.** Offering extra activities like tutoring and support workshops will help students, especially those who are in needs to reach their academic goals.
4. **Examine and Evaluate Chatbot Effectiveness.** Continuously assessing and conducting regular evaluations will help identify the impact of chatbot towards the students' engagement, participation and academic performance
5. **Encourage Equal Learning Tactic.** By promoting the use of combined digital and traditional learning tools will enhance student's learning habits. Fostering a learning environment that merit engagement and academic performance, giving an emphasis in the crucial role of sustaining effort and practice.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The participants of the study were provided detailed information about the research before they were allowed to participate. Those who chose to participate were given consent and assent form adhering to the provisions outlined in the Data Privacy Act of 2012, also known as RA 10173, all responses provided by respondents will be kept private and utilized exclusively for academic purposes. Ensuring the confidentiality of participants' identities and privacy. Additionally, the study strictly followed the

recommended procedures of Memorandum No. 9, s. 2022 for data collection, security of collected data, storage, transfer, and destruction procedures. The participants' identities and other identifying information were not disclosed without their explicit consent. Proper citation and credit were given to the authors mentioned in the study. The researchers upheld the integrity of the data avoiding data fabrication and data falsification, as outlined in the ethical practices. The actual benefit of the study, meeting the needs of the respondents, and encouraging positive change in the classroom will be prioritized. Furthermore, the researchers ensured that after the specific purpose for which the data were gathered and used, the data were no longer retained and were subjected to disposal. To ensure data security and participant privacy, the researcher implemented a comprehensive data disposal protocol. After fulfilling the research objectives, all data were permanently deleted, leaving no possibility of recovery. This involved digital deletion from the Google Form used for data collection, effectively erasing all entries and submissions.

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